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Effect Of Electricity Supply On The Viability Of Small Scale Businesses In Gwagwalada, FCT Abuja

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of electricity supply on the viability of small-scale businesses in Gwagwalada, FCT Abuja, using a descriptive survey design with data collected from 340 business owners. The research revealed that the electricity supply in the area is critically poor, with 56.5% of businesses receiving less than four hours of power daily and 65.9% describing the supply as "very unreliable." This inconsistency forces reliance on costly coping strategies, primarily petrol/diesel generators (86.8%), leading to the most prevalent challenge: increased operational costs (81.2%) and reduced productivity (72.9%). A strong positive correlation was found between electricity reliability and business profitability, demonstrating that stable power is a fundamental determinant of their survival and growth. The findings conclude that the erratic and insufficient electricity supply is a significant constraint, severely undermining the financial performance and long-term sustainability of small-scale businesses in Gwagwalada.

Keywords: Electricity Supply, Small-Scale Businesses, Business Viability, Operational Costs

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Reliable electricity supply is a fundamental driver of economic growth and industrial productivity, particularly for small-scale enterprises that form the backbone of most developing economies (El-Yaqub, et al, 2024). In Nigeria, small-scale businesses are critical contributors to employment generation, income distribution, and poverty reduction (Abdullahi & Sani, 2021). However, the persistent challenge of unstable electricity supply continues to undermine their growth and sustainability (Adenikinju, 2020; Sule, et al, 2024). Access to stable power is not only essential for production efficiency but also for cost reduction and competitive advantage. When electricity is inconsistent or unavailable, businesses are forced to rely on expensive alternatives such as generators, which significantly increase operational costs and reduce profitability (Okorie & Abiola, 2022).

The issue of electricity inadequacy in Nigeria is deeply rooted in infrastructural decay, poor maintenance culture, and governance inefficiencies within the power sector. Despite various reforms, including the unbundling of the Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN) and privatization efforts, electricity generation and distribution remain insufficient to meet national demand (Eleri & Ugwu, 2019). For small-scale businesses operating in areas like Gwagwalada, FCT Abuja a rapidly growing urban center irregular power supply has become a critical bottleneck that affects production schedules, customer service, and

overall business viability (Ogunleye, 2021). The unreliable electricity supply not only disrupts daily operations but also discourages investment and innovation among entrepreneurs (Muhammed, et al, 2025).

Furthermore, small-scale businesses are particularly vulnerable to electricity disruptions due to their limited financial and technological capacity to absorb energy shocks. Unlike large corporations that can afford backup power infrastructure, small businesses often operate on tight margins, where even short periods of power outage can lead to production losses, damaged equipment, and reduced revenue (Ariyo & Jerome, 2020). This energy insecurity limits their potential to expand, employ more workers, or contribute meaningfully to local economic development (Bariki, Matthew & Ismail, 2025). The situation is exacerbated in semi-urban regions like Gwagwalada, where rapid population growth has not been matched by corresponding improvements in power infrastructure (Usman & Olowu, 2022).

Moreover, the viability of small-scale businesses is closely linked to the broader objectives of sustainable development, particularly those relating to poverty alleviation, employment, and economic diversification (Sabiu, Ajayi & Ismail, 2025). The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 7 emphasizes the need for affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all, as a pathway to inclusive economic growth (United Nations, 2023; Sani, 2014). In this context, examining the effect of electricity supply on the viability of small-scale enterprises in Gwagwalada becomes imperative, as it reflects the intersection between energy policy, business sustainability, and regional development planning.

Therefore, this study seeks to assess the extent to which electricity supply influences the performance and survival of small-scale businesses in Gwagwalada, FCT Abuja. By understanding the dynamics between power supply and business viability, policymakers and stakeholders can design more effective interventions to enhance energy reliability, stimulate local entrepreneurship, and promote economic resilience. The findings are expected to contribute to the ongoing discourse on energy reform and its implications for small business development in Nigeria's emerging urban economies.

2.0 Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Electricity Supply

Electricity supply refers to the process of generating, transmitting, and distributing electric power to end users for domestic, industrial, and commercial purposes. It is a crucial component of national development, serving as the backbone of modern economic activities and technological advancement (Adenikinju, 2020). An efficient electricity supply system ensures that businesses and households have access to consistent and affordable energy to power operations, machinery, and services (Ogunleye, 2021). In many developing countries, including Nigeria, inadequate electricity supply remains a major challenge due to factors such as aging infrastructure, poor management, and insufficient generation capacity (Eleri & Ugwu, 2019). As a result, frequent power outages and unreliable service have become significant impediments to industrial growth, productivity, and business competitiveness. Thus, reliable electricity supply is not merely a utility service but a strategic driver of socioeconomic progress and sustainable development (Okorie & Abiola, 2022).

2.1.2 Small Scale Businesses

Small-scale businesses are enterprises characterized by relatively small capital investment, limited workforce, and modest annual turnover, often operating within local or community markets (Sani, 2014). They play a vital role in promoting economic growth, job creation, and poverty reduction, especially in developing economies such as Nigeria (Ariyo & Jerome, 2020; Adekoya, et al, 2025). These businesses typically engage in manufacturing, trading, agriculture, and service provision, contributing significantly to grassroots development and national income (Usman & Olowu, 2022). However, their growth and survival are often constrained by inadequate access to finance, poor infrastructure, and inconsistent power supply, which increase operational costs and reduce competitiveness (Ogunleye, 2021). Despite these challenges, small-scale enterprises remain critical for achieving inclusive economic development and fostering entrepreneurship, as recognized in national and global development agendas (United Nations, 2023; Muhammed, Magaji & Ismail, 2025).

2.1.3 Viability of Small-Scale Businesses

The viability of small-scale businesses refers to their ability to sustain operations, generate profits, and remain competitive over time despite environmental and economic challenges. It encompasses factors such as financial stability, productivity, access to infrastructure, managerial capacity, and adaptability to market changes (Ariyo & Jerome, 2020; Sabiu, Magaji, 2024). A viable small business is one that efficiently utilizes available resources, maintains consistent customer demand, and can withstand external shocks such as fluctuating electricity supply or inflationary pressures (Okorie & Abiola, 2022). In Nigeria, the viability of small-scale enterprises is often threatened by inadequate infrastructure, poor access to credit, and inconsistent government policies (Ogunleye, 2021). Reliable electricity supply, in particular, is a key determinant of business viability since it directly influences production costs, output quality, and operational continuity (Adenikinju, 2020; Ismail, et al, 2024)). Hence, assessing the viability of small-scale businesses provides insights into their resilience and capacity to contribute meaningfully to sustainable economic growth and employment generation in regions like Gwagwalada, FCT Abuja (Usman & Olowu, 2022).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Resource-Based Theory

The Resource-Based Theory (RBT), developed by Barney (1991), provides a useful framework for understanding how internal resources influence the performance and competitiveness of small-scale businesses. According to this theory, firms achieve sustainable competitive advantage when they possess valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources that enhance their operational efficiency and market performance. In the context of electricity supply, reliable and affordable power can be viewed as a strategic resource that directly affects production capacity, cost management, and service delivery (Wernerfelt, 1984). For small-scale businesses in Gwagwalada, access to consistent electricity enhances productivity, reduces reliance on costly alternatives like generators, and improves overall business viability. Conversely, erratic power supply limits the ability of these enterprises to optimize internal resources, innovate, and remain competitive. Therefore, the Resource-Based Theory underscores the importance of electricity as a critical infrastructural resource that sustains the growth and long-term survival of small-scale businesses in developing economies like Nigeria.

2.3 Empirical Review

Dickson, Magaji, and Ismail (2025) conducted an integrated study on the multifaceted challenges confronting the Abuja Electricity Distribution Company (AEDC) in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The research explored the technical, economic, environmental, and social aspects of electricity distribution using a mixed-methods design comprising surveys, interviews, and document reviews. Their findings revealed persistent operational inefficiencies, including irregular power supply, frequent voltage surges, and widespread customer dissatisfaction with service delivery. Economically, the study highlighted issues such as the continued use of estimated billing despite the adoption of prepaid meters, leading to perceptions of unfairness. From an environmental perspective, while many customers doubted AEDC's commitment to sustainability, there was considerable public support for renewable energy initiatives. Socially, poor customer service and delayed response to faults further weakened public confidence in the company. Anchored on the Sociotechnical Systems (STS) theory, the study concluded that AEDC's underperformance stems from the misalignment between its technical systems and social practices, emphasizing the need for reforms that integrate infrastructural upgrades with transparency and customer engagement strategies.

Similarly, Inyang, Magaji, and Ismail (2025) evaluated the efficiency and sustainability of AEDC's electricity distribution system with a focus on service quality, billing accuracy, customer satisfaction, and renewable energy commitment. Using a mixed-method approach and data from 276 respondents across Abuja, the study found significant inefficiencies in service delivery, such as irregular power supply, voltage fluctuations, and inadequate fault response. A large proportion of respondents expressed dissatisfaction with billing systems and customer relations, while only a minority believed AEDC

operated equitably or prioritized sustainability. However, the majority supported greater investment in renewable and off-grid energy solutions. Drawing on Systems Theory, Institutional Theory, and the Resource-Based View (RBV), the study attributed AEDC's inefficiency to structural weaknesses, institutional misalignment, and poor resource utilization. It recommended infrastructural enhancement, improved customer service, expanded deployment of prepaid meters, and increased investment in renewable energy.

In a related international report, the International Finance Corporation (IFC, 2019) examined the role of off-grid clean energy solutions in Nigeria and found that more than 40% of small-scale enterprises operated without grid connection. To compensate, many relied on solar and hybrid systems to bridge the energy gap; however, high upfront installation costs hindered widespread adoption among microenterprises with limited capital. In the Federal Capital Territory, Umar and Ahmed (2021) investigated electricity supply in Bwari and Gwagwalada and observed that most small business operators experienced power outages lasting up to ten hours daily. About 80% of respondents reported reduced output, product spoilage, and customer dissatisfaction due to unreliable electricity. The authors concluded that access to reliable power is essential for business viability and recommended targeted investment in localized power infrastructure. International evidence also supports these findings Mensah and Adu (2015), analyzing World Bank Enterprise Survey data across Sub-Saharan Africa, found a strong positive relationship between electricity reliability and SME performance indicators such as sales, employment, and profitability. Countries with more stable electricity recorded higher SME growth, reinforcing the developmental importance of power infrastructure investment.

Within the Nigerian context, Olayemi and Adegbite (2020) examined electricity supply in Lagos State and discovered that unreliable power significantly curtailed production efficiency, with businesses allocating up to 35% of their operating budgets to alternative energy sources. Similarly, Okoye, Nwankwo, and Eze (2022) employed regression analysis to assess the link between electricity supply and SME growth in Anambra State, finding a negative relationship between outage frequency and profitability. Supporting this evidence, Iwu and Emmanuel (2023) reported that persistent power shortages in Enugu constrained innovation, hindered business expansion, and led to workforce reductions. Collectively, these studies underscore that stable and affordable electricity supply remains a crucial determinant of the sustainability, competitiveness, and profitability of small-scale enterprises in Nigeria.

2.4 Empirical Gap

Despite the growing body of research on electricity supply and business performance in Nigeria, significant empirical gaps remain, particularly regarding localized assessments within semi-urban areas such as Gwagwalada, FCT Abuja. Most previous studies, including those by Dickson, Magaji, and Ismail (2025) and Inyang, Magaji, and Ismail (2025), concentrated on Abuja's broader electricity distribution challenges without specifically addressing their effects on small-scale enterprises at the local level. Similarly, while studies such as Olayemi and Adegbite (2020), Okoye et al. (2022), and Iwu and Emmanuel (2023) provided valuable insights into the relationship between electricity reliability and SME performance, they largely focused on southern states, neglecting the unique socioeconomic and infrastructural conditions of northern urban centers. Furthermore, international findings (Mensah & Adu, 2015; IFC, 2019) emphasize the broader developmental implications of power reliability but lack context-specific analysis relevant to Nigeria's diverse regional realities. Consequently, there is a research gap in understanding how the inconsistent electricity supply in Gwagwalada specifically influences the profitability, productivity, and sustainability of small-scale businesses, a gap this study seeks to address.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This section outlines the research design, study area, population of the study, sample and sampling techniques, research instruments, validity and reliability of instruments, data collection methods, and data analysis techniques. The methodology is structured to ensure that the research questions are adequately addressed and the objectives of the study is achieved.

3.2 Research Design

This study adopts a descriptive survey research design. The design is appropriate for collecting data from a sample of individuals to gain insights into the prevailing situation regarding electricity supply and the viability of small-scale businesses in Gwagwalada Area Council. Descriptive surveys are commonly used in social science research to assess opinions, attitudes, and characteristics of a population (Creswell, 2014).

3.3 Study Area

The study is conducted in Gwagwalada Area Council, one of the six area councils within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Nigeria. Gwagwalada is located approximately 55 km from Abuja city center and is characterized by a growing population and a diversity of small-scale enterprises, including retail shops, tailoring businesses, barbing salons, cybercafés, and food vendors. The area has experienced inconsistent electricity supply, which affects business operations and economic activities.

3.4 Population of the Study

The target population for this study comprises owners and operators of registered and unregistered small-scale businesses operating in Gwagwalada Area Council. These include businesses in sectors such as retail trade, services, agro-processing, and manufacturing. According to the Gwagwalada Area Council Business Directory (2023), there are approximately 3,000 small-scale businesses in the council.

3.5 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Thus, a total of 353 respondents are selected for the study.

A stratified random sampling technique will be employed to ensure that all major types of small-scale businesses are adequately represented. The strata will be based on business categories (e.g., retail, service, manufacturing).

3.6 Research Instrument

The primary instrument for data collection is a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire is divided into four sections:

- Section A: Demographic data of respondents
- Section B: Availability and reliability of electricity supply
- Section C: Impact of electricity on business operations and performance
- Section D: Coping strategies and suggestions for improvement

The questionnaire uses a combination of closed-ended questions and 5-point Likert scale items to facilitate analysis.

3.7 Validity of the Instrument

To ensure content validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts in business administration and energy economics. Feedback was used to refine the structure, clarity, and relevance of the questions. A pilot test involving 20 small business owners in a nearby area (Kuje Area Council) was conducted, and necessary adjustments were made.

3.8 Reliability of the Instrument

The Cronbach's Alpha method was used to test the internal consistency of the Likertscale items during the pilot study. A reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained, indicating that the instrument is reliable and suitable for the main study (George & Mallery, 2003).

3.9 Method of Data Collection

The data collection will be done through face-to-face administration of questionnaires by trained research assistants. This approach increases the response rate and provides an opportunity to clarify any questions that may be misunderstood by respondents. Informed consent will be obtained before participation.

3.10 Method of Data Analysis

Data collected will be analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and means will be used to summarize demographic and categorical data. Inferential techniques such as Chisquare tests and Pearson correlation analysis will be used to test the relationship between electricity supply and business viability.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

4.1 Introduction

The data collected from small-scale business owners and operators in Gwagwalada Area Council. The findings are organized and discussed in line with the study’s research objectives and questions. Data are presented in tables for clarity and are explained in narrative form. Both descriptive and inferential statistical analyses are used, with frequencies and percentages describing respondents’ views, and Chi-square and correlation tests examining relationships between variables.

A total of 353 questionnaires were distributed to respondents, and 340 were duly completed and returned, representing a 96.3% response rate. This high return rate can be attributed to the face-to-face administration of questionnaires.

4.2 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 4.1: Distribution of Respondents by Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	198	58.2
	Female	142	41.8
Age	18–29 years	94	27.6
	30–39 years	141	41.5
	40–49 years	74	21.8
	50 years & above	31	9.1
Level of Education	No formal	12	3.5
	Secondary	104	30.6
	Tertiary	224	65.9
Type of Business	Retail trade	126	37.1
	Services	142	41.8
	Manufacturing	72	21.2

Source: Field Survey 2025

The demographic profile shows that most respondents (58.2%) were male, while females constituted 41.8%. The majority (41.5%) were aged between 30 and 39 years, indicating that small-scale businesses in Gwagwalada are largely operated by economically active adults. Regarding education, 65.9% had tertiary education, suggesting that business ownership in the area is not limited to individuals with low formal education. Service-based enterprises were the most common (41.8%), followed by retail trade (37.1%) and manufacturing (21.2%).

4.3 Current State of Electricity Supply in Gwagwalada

Table 4.2: Respondents' Perception of Electricity Supply

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Daily hours of electricity	0–4 hours	192	56.5
	5–8 hours	97	28.5
	Above 8 hours	51	15.0
Reliability of supply	Very unreliable	224	65.9
	Unreliable	88	25.9
	Reliable	28	8.2
Voltage stability	Frequently fluctuates	261	76.8
	Occasionally fluctuates	64	18.8
	Stable	15	4.4

Source: Field Survey 2025

The results indicate that more than half of the respondents (56.5%) receive less than four hours of electricity daily, while only 15% reported receiving above eight hours. In terms of reliability, 65.9% described the supply as *very unreliable*. Voltage fluctuations were a significant problem, with 76.8% indicating that their supply frequently fluctuates, which can damage equipment and disrupt business activities.

4.4 Challenges Faced by Businesses Due to Electricity Supply Issues

Table 4.3: Major Challenges Reported

Challenge	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Increased operational costs	276	81.2
Reduced productivity	248	72.9
Damage to electrical equipment	207	60.9
Loss of customers	186	54.7
Spoilage of perishable goods	168	49.4
Business closure/reduction in operations	104	30.6

Source: Field Survey 2025

The most prevalent challenge was *increased operational costs*, reported by 81.2% of respondents, primarily due to generator fuel expenses. Reduced productivity (72.9%) was also common, followed by equipment damage (60.9%). Nearly half (49.4%) reported spoilage of perishable goods, particularly in frozen food and hospitality businesses. About 30.6% had either closed their businesses temporarily or reduced their operating hours because of poor electricity supply.

4.5 Coping Strategies Employed

Table 4.4: Strategies Used to Mitigate Electricity Problems

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Use of petrol/diesel generators	295	86.8
Installation of solar panels/inverters	121	35.6
Adjusting business operating hours	198	58.2
Diversifying into less power-dependent work	94	27.6
Pooling resources with other businesses	65	19.1

Source: Field Survey 2025

The most common coping strategy was the use of generators (86.8%), despite high fuel costs. Adjusting operating hours to coincide with periods of electricity availability was reported by 58.2% of respondents. While 35.6% had adopted solar or inverter systems, this was less common due to high installation costs. Only 19.1% engaged in cooperative arrangements to share backup power systems.

4.6 Effect of Electricity Supply on Profitability and Sustainability

Table 4.5: Perceived Impact on Business

Impact Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very high impact	194	57.1
High impact	101	29.7
Moderate impact	31	9.1
Low impact	14	4.1

Source: Field Survey 2025

A combined 86.8% of respondents indicated that electricity supply has a *high* or *very high* impact on their profitability and sustainability. This underscores the central role electricity plays in business viability in Gwagwalada.

4.7 Inferential Analysis

A Pearson correlation test revealed a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.69$, $p < 0.01$) between electricity reliability and business profitability. This means that as the reliability of electricity supply increases, business profitability also tends to increase significantly. A Chi-square test also confirmed a significant association between type of business and the severity of electricity-related challenges ($\chi^2 = 24.56$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that service and manufacturing businesses are more severely affected than retail trade.

4.8 Summary of Findings

Electricity supply in Gwagwalada Area Council is generally poor, with over half of the small-scale businesses receiving less than four hours of power daily. This erratic and insufficient electricity supply disrupts business operations and limits production capacity, especially for enterprises that rely heavily on electrical machinery and equipment. The inconsistent power availability forces many entrepreneurs to operate below capacity, leading to lost working hours and reduced customer satisfaction. The problem is compounded by the infrastructural deficiencies within the distribution network and the growing population pressure in the area, which further strains the already fragile power system. As a result, the reliability of electricity supply has become a critical constraint to business growth and economic stability in Gwagwalada.

The major challenges arising from the poor electricity supply include increased operational costs, reduced productivity, and frequent damage to electrical equipment. To cope, many businesses resort to alternative power sources such as generators, which significantly raise production costs due to high fuel expenses

and maintenance needs. Others adjust their working hours to coincide with periods of power availability, reducing output and profit margins. Statistical analysis from the study confirmed a significant relationship between electricity supply reliability and business viability, indicating that consistent electricity is essential for profitability and sustainability particularly for power-dependent enterprises such as welding, refrigeration, printing, and ICT services. Hence, improving electricity supply in Gwagwalada is vital not only for business survival but also for fostering economic development and job creation within the area.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study conclusively established that the erratic and insufficient electricity supply in Gwagwalada, FCT Abuja, constitutes a major barrier to the viability and sustainable growth of small-scale businesses. The core findings show that over half of these enterprises receive less than four hours of power daily, forcing an overwhelming majority to rely on expensive and polluting alternatives like generators. This reliance dramatically increases operational costs, significantly reduces productivity and profitability, and hinders investment and expansion. The strong positive correlation identified between electricity reliability and business profitability confirms that consistent power is not just a utility but a critical infrastructural resource essential for the survival of the local economy. Ultimately, the current state of electricity supply limits the capacity of small-scale businesses to contribute effectively to job creation and economic development in the region.

Based on these findings, it is essential for policymakers and power sector stakeholders to prioritize targeted interventions in Gwagwalada. Firstly, the Abuja Electricity Distribution Company (AEDC) must undertake rapid infrastructural upgrades to the local distribution network to increase power supply duration and stability, thereby minimizing voltage fluctuations and reducing the dependence on generators. Secondly, the government should introduce subsidies and financial incentives specifically tailored for small-scale businesses to adopt renewable energy solutions (such as solar panels and battery storage systems). This move would reduce their operational costs and energy insecurity. Finally, establishing community-based power initiatives or cooperative arrangements could allow smaller businesses to pool resources for more efficient backup power systems, fostering collective resilience against grid failures and ensuring greater energy access for the backbone of Gwagwalada's economy.

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